

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2021-22 academic year for BPT

INTRODUCTION TO COMPUTERS

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

Value Added Course on
Introduction to Computers

15 weeks (30
hours) training

What to learn?

- Genesis of computer
- Introduction to MS Word
- Introduction to MS Excel
- Introduction to MS Powerpoint

For BPT undergraduates (2021 Batch)

 Srinivas University city campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru

 0824-2429139

Course period	From July 2022 till October 2022, during 2 nd semester (15 weeks)
Duration	30 hours (2 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	BPT 1 st year undergraduates (2021 batch)

Course Objectives:

1. Introduce the fundamentals of computing devices and reinforce computer vocabulary, particularly with respect to personal use of computer hardware and software, the Internet and networking.
2. Provide hands-on use of Microsoft Office applications Word, Excel and PowerPoint.
3. Provide foundational or “computer literacy” curriculum that prepares students for life-long learning of computer concepts and skills.

Course Outcomes:

CO1. Will acquire knowledge about basics of computer applications.

CO2. Get familiarity in Word Processing software, Spread sheet, and power point presentations.

CO3. Develop skills in internet accessibility and download the relevant subject matter files/documents.

CO4. Learn the use of Internet services for research and documentation.

COURSE OUTLINE		
MODULE	TOPIC	HOURS
1	Introduction to Computers: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Generations of Computers and Classifications of Computers.• Computer Peripherals - Input and Output devices, Central Processor Unit (CPU) , Architecture of a digital computer, Memory unit ALU, Control Unit-Data Processing Systems & Stages.	4
2	Introduction to windows: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• History, features, desktop, taskbar, icons on the desktop, operation with folder, creating shortcuts, operation with windows (opening, closing, moving, resizing, minimizing and maximizing, etc.)	6
3	Introduction to programming, Ms word & Excel: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Introduction to Programming Languages, Data processing techniques, Modes of data processing, Flowcharting techniques.• Introduction to MS-word: Introduction, components of a word window, creating, opening and inserting files, editing a document file, page setting and formatting the text, saving the document, spell checking, printing the document file, creating and editing of table, mail merge.• Introduction to Excel: Introduction, about worksheet, entering information, saving workbooks and formatting, printing the worksheet, creating graphs.	12
4	Introduction to Power-point: Introduction, creating and manipulating presentation, views, formatting and enhancing text, slide with graphs.	8

Attendance Policy

The course requires compulsory 75% attendance and only in this case a student will be issued a certificate.

Text/Reference Books:

1. Maluth J. M. Basic Computer Knowledge, 2016.
2. Nagpal D. P. A New Approach to Basic Computer Education, 2nd ed. S. Chand and Company Ltd, 2012.
3. R. S Salaria. Computer fundamentals. Khanna publishing 2017.
4. Ajaysinh K Jadeja. Computer basics for medical professionals. 1st ed. The National book depot: Mumbai, 2015.

E-Resources:

1. <https://youtu.be/Hizdc4XVJ1E>
2. <https://youtu.be/S-nHYzK-BVg>
3. <https://youtu.be/rwbho0CgEAE>
4. <https://youtu.be/XF34-Wu6qWU>

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

Certificate of Completion

presented to

AARON RENY (5SU21PT001)

for attending and completing value added course on " Introduction to Computers" from
July 2022 to October 2022

Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
Associate Professor
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
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ABDUL JABBAR K (5SU21PT002)

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Total Hours- 30

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ABHINENDHU G S (5SU21PT003)

for attending and completing value added course on " Introduction to Computers" from
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Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
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Certificate of Completion

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ABHIRAM V K (5SU21PT004)

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Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
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Certificate of Completion

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ADIL ROSHAN K (5SU21PT005)

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Total Hours- 30

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AFEEDA BAIJU (5SU21PT006)

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Total Hours- 30

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AFEFAH ABDUL KHADAR (5SU21PT007)

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Total Hours- 30

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AFRAZ ASHRAF (5SU21PT008)

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Total Hours- 30

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AJITH K S (5SU21PT009)

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ANANYA (5SU21PT010)

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ANUSHA (5SU21PT013)

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APARNA T R (5SU21PT014)

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ARJUN ASHOK (5SU21PT015)

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ARTHANA SURESH K V (5SU21PT016)

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ARYA PARVATHY P (5SU21PT018)

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ASWIN SANTHOSH (5SU21PT019)

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ATHULYA PANOLI (5SU21PT020)

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AVANI A K (5SU21PT021)

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AYSHA NAJEEB (5SU21PT022)

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B PRATHEEK PAI (5SU21PT023)

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BHATATE VINAY MAHESH (5SU21PT024)

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CHAITHRA P M (5SU21PT025)

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DHRUVE V S (5SU21PT026)

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DILNA FEMI K (5SU21PT027)

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FATHIHA ISRA K P (5SU21PT028)

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FATHIMA NAJA (5SU21PT029)

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FATHIMA NISHA (5SU21PT030)

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FATHIMATHU HASRA M K P (5SU21PT031)

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FELNA A K (5SU21PT032)

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HAFEEZA FATHIMA (5SU21PT033)

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HASHIM ABOOBACKER (5SU21PT034)

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HIBA NAZIR (5SU21PT035)

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HUDHA GAFOOR (5SU21PT036)

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HUSSAIN RAHIM (5SU21PT037)

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IBRAHIM JUNAID (5SU21PT038)

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JADHAV ABHIJIT SANJAY (5SU21PT039)

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JIDIN PARAMEKATTIL BHASY (5SU21PT040)

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K M MIDLAJ (5SU21PT041)

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KADEEJA A (5SU21PT042)

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KADIJATHUL ESHANA (5SU21PT043)

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KARUNYA (5SU21PT044)

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LEKSHMI T (5SU21PT045)

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M CHAITHANYA (5SU21PT046)

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MARIYAM SAFA (5SU21PT047)

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MASHHOORA V (5SU21PT048)

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MEENAKSHI PRADEEP (5SU21PT049)

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MINHA K (5SU21PT050)

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MOHAMMAD HASHIM K A (5SU21PT051)

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MOHAMMED ARSHAD K (5SU21PT054)

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MUFEEDA THASNI (5SU21PT057)

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MUFEETHA M V (5SU21PT058)

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MUHAMMAD SHA S (5SU21PT059)

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Certificate of Completion

presented to

NAJI MUHAMMED (5SU21PT063)

for attending and completing value added course on " Introduction to Computers" from
July 2022 to October 2022

Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
Associate Professor
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean
Institute of Physiotherapy

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Certificate of Completion

presented to

NANDANA P S (5SU21PT064)

for attending and completing value added course on " Introduction to Computers" from
July 2022 to October 2022

Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
Associate Professor
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

Certificate of Completion

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NANDHANA V S (5SU21PT065)

for attending and completing value added course on " Introduction to Computers" from
July 2022 to October 2022

Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
Associate Professor
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
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Certificate of Completion

presented to

NEHA (5SU21PT066)

for attending and completing value added course on " Introduction to Computers" from
July 2022 to October 2022

Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
Associate Professor
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
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Certificate of Completion

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NIDEESHA ALVA (5SU21PT067)

for attending and completing value added course on " Introduction to Computers" from
July 2022 to October 2022

Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
Associate Professor
Course Instructor

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NIDHI M S (5SU21PT068)

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July 2022 to October 2022

Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
Associate Professor
Course Instructor

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PAKRUDDEEN AHMED MIDLAJ (5SU21PT069)

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July 2022 to October 2022

Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
Associate Professor
Course Instructor

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PARINITHA M NAIK (5SU21PT070)

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Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
Associate Professor
Course Instructor

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POOJARY NEHA YOGESH (5SU21PT071)

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Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
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Course Instructor

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PRATHYUL GHOSH C (5SU21PT072)

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July 2022 to October 2022

Total Hours- 30

Dr. Premkumar M
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Course Instructor

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RIYA FATHIMA (5SU21PT073)

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RIYA SANTHOSH (5SU21PT074)

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ROOSA FIDHA (5SU21PT075)

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S R POOVARASI (5SU21PT076)

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SAHANA K S (5SU21PT077)

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SANDRA SATHAR (5SU21PT078)

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SANDWANA MANIKUTTAN (5SU21PT079)

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SANGEETH KRISHNA K S (5SU21PT080)

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SANJANA A (5SU21PT081)

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SHAIKH TASMIYA NASIR (5SU21PT082)

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SHAMIL HASHIQ (5SU21PT083)

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SHAMLA A U (5SU21PT084)

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SHASHANK K (5SU21PT085)

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SHEHREBANO BOHRA (5SU21PT086)

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SHIMNA K N (5SU21PT088)

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SHREE VIDYA (5SU21PT089)

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SHREYA B (5SU21PT090)

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SIDAN K C (5SU21PT091)

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ROSHAN P R (5SU21PT097)

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AHAMMAD MUKTHAR (5SU21PT098)

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